

**ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS, WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE
TO CHANGE IN ATTITUDE, IN ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT**

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Abstract:

Sustainable development is very crucial for the survival of the human race. Sustainability means meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generation to meet their own needs. Due to extreme weather changes, pollution, forest and soil degradation, animal extinction and deterioration in quality of environmental factors. It is high time now to focus and put efforts for sustainable development.

To achieve this, one of the important aspect is related to psychology of the people. Their understanding of the issue, accepting their role, in solving the issue and making desirable changes in their own thinking, habits, attitudes and behaviour is very important in achieving the goals of sustainable development. Our attitudes are our evaluation of the outside world, either negative or positive, it is a way how we look at the things, which has serious impact on our behaviour. It is needed to change our attitude in such a way so that we will be able to achieve the goals of sustainable development.

Key terms – *sustainable development, psychology, attitude.*

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Objectives:

1. To understand meaning and importance of sustainable development
2. To understand meaning and importance of attitude in our behavior
3. To suggest some ways to change our attitude leading to achievement of sustainable development goal

Introduction:

It is said that the environment is everybody's concern as we all are part of it, born and brought up in the lap of nature, we consume it, we survive, we breath and we are inseparable part of it. We all know that due to Industrialization, construction activities, urbanization, pollution, use of vehicles, excessive deforestation, changing attitudes, attraction of materiastic life, use and throw approach without taking care of nature has lead to all serious environmental issues. Some of them are pollution, climate change, depletion of O Zone layer, scarcity of resources, desertification of fertile land etc., Not only this, but environmental degradation including destruction of ecosystem, habitat destruction and the extinction of wildlife. This is very alarming threat for the world and the answer will be sustainable development. We need to work for achieving the 17 sustainable goals such as No Poverty, Zero hunger, Good health and well being, Gender equality etc., The achievement of these goals is possible only with the participation of people throughout the world.

We need to understand that the psychology of people plays very important role in every issue and so it true with sustainable development for ex. unless people change their attitude about health, environment, poverty etc., they will not change their behavior. Attitude refers to a set of emotions, beliefs and behaviors towards a particular object, person, thing or event and they can have powerful impact on our behavior and therefore in achieving sustainable development, which requires conservation of environment, we must change our habits, attitudes, behavior and lifestyle in a way which will enable us to protect, conserve our environment. Following are some suggestions to accept & to implement to protect our mother earth through sustainable development.

Suggestions:

1. We must understand that we are just a part of this environment. We are not the masters of the environment.
2. We must try to adopt eco-friendly lifestyle right from use of various products to celebration of various religious festivals for ex instead of thermacol use of eco-friendly material in Ganpati festival.
3. Avoiding wastage of food during marriage and other ceremonies
4. Making, accepting proper consumption of resources as our moral duty towards mother

earth and try to save every drop of water, energy and other resources.

5. Recognizing the role of women in protecting nature as they have very emotional connection with nature as described in eco-feminism.
6. Government and environmentalist must take efforts to create awareness about eco-friendly life styles. For ex-less creation of noise/voice/sounds, avoiding use of non-degradable plastic, use of cotton cloth, proper use of paper,fuel,energy and water.
7. Through education and syllabus young generation must be taught about nature friendly life style and its importance in sustainable development. Some of our old traditions, which use to conserve nature must be respected & implemented such as planting of basil plant in our home.
8. Changing our habits of using excessive water, vehicles, artificial beauty products, frequently changing electronic articles such as mobiles, air conditioner etc,to reduce electronic waste and health hazards.
9. We must create mechanisms for better management of water, sanitation, waste material, garbage, plastic and various chemicals and other related polluting materials. We must learn to repair, reuse and recycle various resources, even in our home.
10. On a country level, we must contribute for less omission of carbon dioxide for reducing global warming.
11. We must undertake for clean ups and changing our attitudes for ex. We must do out shopping wisely, not to buy unnecessary articles and things and support to eco-friendly products such as use of LED bulbs, use of herbal insecticides etc.,

Apart from these – we must change our habits as follows.

1. Turn off lights and fan when not needed.
2. Try to use organic foods and eco-friendly products
3. Collect information about conservation of Environment and work on it.
4. Accept the responsibility of protecting nature and implement it through your habits and lifestyle.
5. We must understand that nature is not a place to visit but it is our home and so we must make the goal of our life to live in agreement with nature.

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